

An Environmentally Friendly Modified Wet-Filament Winding Process

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SUMMARY

This paper reports on a modified wet-filament winding process where the conventional resin bath was replaced with a custom-designed resin impregnation unit, a resin dispensing unit and a static mixer. This new manufacturing technique resulted in a significant reduction in the consumption of solvents and generation of waste resin.

Keywords: Composites, Wet-filament winding, Environmentally friendly manufacture, Resin injection, Mechanical testing

INTRODUCTION

Conventional wet-filament winding is generally used to manufacture components such as pipes, pressure vessels and printer-rollers. A schematic illustration of conventional wet-filament winding is shown in Figure 1. With reference to Figure 1, the reinforcing fibre tows (A) from creels or bobbins (B) are fed through a tensioning device (C) into a resin bath (D). The fibres are then fed through a traversing carriage (E) which lays down the resin-impregnated fibres in a pre-determined fashion along the length of the rotating mandrel (F). The individual components of the resin system (for example, epoxy and amine) are mixed in the required stoichiometric proportions and are poured into the resin bath (D).

Figure 1. A schematic illustration of conventional wet-filament winding.

Some of the practical and environmental issues associated with conventional wet-filament winding are as follows:

(i) *The resin bath:* The resin and hardener are generally weighed out and mixed manually prior to transferring the mixed resin system to the resin bath. Open-top resin baths can result in significant emissions of low molecular weight components from the resin system to the atmosphere.

(ii) *Solvent consumption:* Since thermosetting resins are used in wet-filament winding, the resin bath and all the machinery that comes into contact with the mixed resin system has to be cleaned thoroughly with solvent after each production run. This is necessary to prevent any residual mixed resin from setting into an infusible solid on, or in, the processing equipment. Subsequent to the cleaning operation, the solvent must be recovered and disposed.

(iii) *Waste resin:* Depending on the volume of the resin bath and the mode of impregnation used, a proportion of the resin is retained in the resin bath at the end of a production run. This excess resin has to be cross-linked and disposed.

(iv) *Legislation:* A current trend in legislation means that a number of the above-mentioned issues will need to be addressed. For example, air-quality in the workplace, permissible exposure limits for the workforce with regard to specified chemicals and solvents, recycling of solvents and waste minimisation.

The following section describes the development of an environmentally friendly wet-filament winding process that addresses some of the issues listed above; this manufacturing technique will be referred to as “clean filament winding”.

METHODOLOGY

(i) **Clean filament winding design details:** A schematic illustration of the modified or clean filament winding (CFW) manufacturing technique is presented in Figure 2. On comparing Figures 1 and 2, it can be seen that in the CFW manufacturing process, the resin bath has been replaced by a resin delivery system, a fibre “spreading” station and a resin impregnation unit. The details of each of these items are presented below.

Figure 2. A schematic illustration of the modified wet-filament winding manufacturing technique. The highlighted components are: (A) Fibre bundles; (B) Fibre creels; (C) Tensioning system and fibre guides; (D) Fibre spreading station; (E) Resin impregnation unit; (F) Resin delivery system; (G) Traversing carriage; and (H) Mandrel.

(a) *Resin/hardener delivery system:* In the CFW process, the resin and hardener are stored in separate containers and pumped on-demand using a pair of precision gear-pumps to a static mixer. The precision pumps used in this study were capable of delivering $10\text{-}110\text{ g}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of resin and hardener and capable of handling liquids with viscosities of $20\text{-}10,000\text{ mPa}\cdot\text{s}$. The resin dispensing unit was manufactured by Dispensing Liquid, UK.

(b) *Fibre spreading station:* A key feature of the CFW process is the induced spreading of the fibre tows prior to impregnation. Fibre-spreading effectively reduces the “thickness” of the fibre tows and facilitates faster and more effective transverse impregnation. A schematic illustration of the fibre spreading station is shown in Figure 3. In this study, a Taguchi analysis was used to investigate and determine the significance of various winding parameters. This investigation is described in greater detail in part (iii d) of the methodology section.

(c) *Resin impregnation unit:* A number of prototypes were investigated and this paper reports on prototype-V (shown in Figure 4). Here, the fibres from the spreading-station undergo further spreading when they traverse an entry pin (A). This pin can be profiled and is used to induce further spreading of the fibres. The mixed resin system from the static mixer is delivered to the impregnation zone/reservoir (B) via a resin feed channel (C) that is machined through the top injection pin (D). The relative dimensions of the key components associated with prototype-V are shown in Figure 4.

Unlike conventional wet-filament winding, the volume of the reservoir is approximately $1.2 \times 10^{-5}\text{ m}^3$; this impregnation unit was capable of handling a maximum of four (1200 Tex) fibre bundles. This represents a significant reduction in volume when compared to a five-litre resin bath. Therefore, the volume of resin that has to be disposed at the end of a production run represents that contained in the static mixer ($6 \times 10^{-6}\text{ m}^3$) and the resin impregnator ($1.2 \times 10^{-5}\text{ m}^3$). Likewise, the volume of solvent required to clean the resin impregnation unit is significantly smaller than that needed for a five-litre resin bath-based impregnation system. The effective free-surface areas of the mixed resin system for a five litre resin bath with a rotating drum (for resin pick-up) and the current resin impregnation unit are 0.448 m^2 and 0.005 m^2 respectively. As a result, the emissions to the atmosphere are also reduced significantly in the CFW process. Moreover, in the CFW process, the resin impregnation unit is located directly over the rotating mandrel. This eliminates the need to clean up any resin drips from the impregnated fibre bundles.

Figure 3.

Figure 3. A schematic illustration of the fibre spreading station, showing: (A) A concave spreading roller/pin; and (B) A convex spreading roller/pin.

Figure 4.

Figure 4. A schematic illustration of prototype-V, showing: (A) Entry pin; (B) Impregnation zone/reservoir; (C) Resin feed channel; and (D) Injection pin.

(ii) Filament winding trials

The term “conventional” is used here to describe the filament wound tubes that were manufactured using a conventional resin bath (4-axis filament winding machine, Pultrex, UK). This machine was not available for subsequent trials and therefore a custom-made filament winding machine (Coil Winding Technology, UK) was used to manufacture filament wound tubes using the CFW technique. The optimisation of fibre spreading was also undertaken using this filament winding machine. The CFW technique was also used at an industrial site (Halyard Precision Composites, UK) to manufacture filament wound samples. In all cases, the resin system used was Araldyte LY3505 resin and XB3403 hardener (Huntsman Advanced Materials, UK). The glass fibres used in these trials were E-Glass 1200 Tex (PPG Industries, UK). The approximate winding speed was 10 m/minute. Once the required amount of impregnated fibre was laid down on the mandrel, the assembly was transferred to an air-circulating oven and processed at 70 °C for 6 hours. The ovens used in the three trials were different and furthermore, the mandrel was rotated during processing at 70 °C for the conventional and industrial trials. A simple mandrel extraction unit was used to remove the filament wound tubes after processing in the oven.

(iii) Evaluation of filament wound composites

The following tests were conducted to evaluate the filament wound composites. With reference to the filament wound tubes that were manufactured at the industrial site using the CFW technique, only fibre volume fraction and void content results are presented.

(a) Fibre volume fraction and void content

The fibre volume fraction and void content of the filament wound tubes were carried out in accordance with ASTM standard D2584 [1] and D2734 [2] respectively. Test specimens (20 mm width and length) were cut from the filament wound tubes using a diamond-coated cutting wheel. The mass of the test specimens were measured using a five-digit analytical balance. The “burn-off” tests were carried out in a muffle-furnace at 575 °C for 10 hours.

(b) Image analysis

Samples of 20 x 20 mm were cut using a diamond-coated wheel and mounted using an epoxy adhesive. The potted samples were polished using conventional metallographic procedures. A Leitz DMRX microscope and image analysis station was used to obtain a minimum of 20 images at random.

(c) Hoop tensile strength (split-disk)

The procedures stipulated in ASTM D2290 [3] were used to obtain the hoop tensile strengths of the filament wound tubes manufactured using the conventional and CFW techniques. Rings of 20 mm width with notches (3.2 mm radius) were cut from the filament wound tubes. A schematic illustration of the test fixture, with the appropriate dimensions, is shown in Figure 5. These tests were carried out at room temperature on a Zwick-1484 machine using a cross-head displacement rate of 2 mm/min.

(d) Evaluation of fibre spreading using Taguchi analysis

The apparatus illustrated in Figure 3 was used to study the parameters that could influence the degree of fibre spreading. The rationale for this investigation was based on

Figure 6 where the time required to achieve transverse impregnation of a fibre tow as a function of the thickness of the tow is presented. Figure 6 was generated using Equation 1 [4], where t_i is impregnation time, T_0 is initial impregnation thickness, η is viscosity, V_f is fibre volume fraction, c_1 and c_2 are constants, K_t is transverse permeability and ΔP is a pressure differential.

$$t_i = \eta(1 - V_f) T_0^2 \left[\frac{c_1^2 \left(\ln \left(\frac{1}{c_1} \right)^2 + 1 \right) - c_2^2 \left(\ln \left(\frac{1}{c_2} \right)^2 + 1 \right)}{4K_t(\Delta P)} \right] \quad (1)$$

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 5. A photograph of the hoop tensile test fixture.

Figure 6. A graph showing the effect of fibre tow thickness variations on transverse impregnation [4].

With reference to Figure 6 it can clearly be seen that fibre tow thickness has an important role in transverse impregnation. This graph shows that as a fibre is spread out, its transverse impregnation time will be decreased.

The “Taguchi method” [5] was used to assess the relevance of the following parameters to aid fibre spreading: (i) contact length between the fibre tows and the cylindrical pins of the fibre spreading station; (ii) winding speed; (iii) fibre spreading fixture configuration (pin or roller); and (iv) the number of fibre spreading fixtures. These input factors are summarised in Table 1a where two levels have been specified per parameter corresponding to a minimum (Level 1) and maximum (Level 2). For example, the filament winding speeds at Levels 1 and 2 were set at 2.5 m/min (minimum) and 10 m/min (maximum) respectively.

As four input factors with two level variations were investigated, a 2^4 Taguchi matrix (known as L_{16}) was used for this study. This matrix produced a set of 16 experiments which allowed an analysis of each input factor for the two level variations. Table 1b shows the Taguchi matrix used in this study. The important columns of Table 1b are A, B, D and H, these columns defined the level settings for the four factors for each experiment. For example, the conditions of experiment 1 are: 2.5 cm contact length (Level 1, shown in column A); 2.5 m/ min winding speed (Level 1, shown in column B); roller fixture (Level 1, shown in column D); and 1 pin (Level 1, shown in column H). Each experiment condition was repeated 5 times and an average degree of fibre

spreading for the experiments was taken. The fibre spreading station and the resin impregnation unit shown in Figure 3 and 4 respectively were used in this study. The degree of fibre spreading was recorded by using a charge-coupled device camera. Figure 7 shows typical images of a fibre tow in the as-received condition (A) and after experiencing maximum spreading (B).

Table 1a. Input factors for the L₁₆ Taguchi analysis.

Factors	Level 1	Level 2
A Contact Length (cm)	2.5	10
B Winding Speed (ml/min)	2.5	10
D Fixture Configuration	Roller	Pin
H Number of Fixtures	1	2
Interactions		
C Contact Length vs Winding Speed	-	-
E Contact Length vs Fixture Configuration	-	-
F Winding Speed vs Fixture Configuration	-	-
G Contact Length vs Number of Pins	-	-
I Winding Speed vs Number of Pins	-	-
J Fixture Configuration vs Number of Pins	-	-

Table 1b. L₁₆ Taguchi array

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
3	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	1
4	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
5	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	2
6	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1
7	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	2
8	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1
9	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1
10	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	1	2
11	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1
12	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
13	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	2
14	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1
15	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2
16	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	1

Figure 7. (A) A photograph of an as-received fibre tow. (B) A photograph of a fibre tow after fibre spreading.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(i) Clean filament winding design concept

Issues relating to the manual mixing of the resin and hardener during the conventional filament winding process were overcome during the CFW process by using precision gear-pumps to deliver the resin and hardener to a KenicsTM static mixer. This approach also meant that the required stoichiometry of the two components could be controlled accurately [6]. Feed-back control between the resin dispenser and the rotation speed of the mandrel facilitated accurate metering of the mixed resin system to the resin impregnation unit.

The resin impregnation unit used in the CFW method is shown to vastly reduce the amount of waste resin produced and cleaning solvent consumed for the production of filament wound tubes. These reductions can be attributed to the decreased volume of the resin impregnation unit ($1.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3$) in comparison to a five-litre resin bath. Furthermore, the volume of solvent required to clean the resin impregnation unit is significantly lower than that needed for a five-litre resin bath. The effective free-surface

areas of the mixed resin system for a five-litre resin bath with a rotating drum (for resin pick-up) and the current resin impregnation unit are 0.448 m² and 0.005 m² respectively. Therefore, the emissions to the atmosphere are also reduced significantly in the CFW process. Moreover, in the CFW process, the resin injection unit is located directly above the mandrel, eliminating the need to clean up any resin drips from the impregnated fibre bundles.

Fibre spreading plays a key role in the CFW process. This study has established that pins and rollers are effective in inducing fibre spreading. A number of techniques have been reported in the literature to induce fibre spreading [7-9]. A balance must be maintained between the number of fixtures that are used to induce fibre spreading and the resultant increase in tension in the fibres. The data presented in Figure 6 clearly shows the effect of fibre tow thickness on the transverse impregnation rate.

(ii) Filament winding trials

With reference to the filament winding trials that were undertaken at the industrial site, notable features of the exercise were as follows. (a) The retrofitting of the resin impregnation unit onto the commercial filament winding machine required a simple adapter plate to secure it in position. (b) The time taken to clean prototype-V at the end of the trial was approximately 5 minutes in comparison to 60 minutes needed for a conventional five-litre resin bath with a rotating drum-based impregnator system. Issues relating to solvent consumption were discussed previously. The quality of the composites manufactured using the conventional resin bath, CFW and a CFW-retrofitted system on a industrial machine (on-site) are discussed in the following section.

(iii) Evaluation of filament wound composites

(a) Fibre volume fraction and void content

Appreciating the fact that the filament wound samples were produced on three different filament winding machines but using the same fibre and resin system, a summary of the fibre volume fractions and void contents are presented in Table 2. The results from the trials using resin impregnator prototype-IV have also been included in Table 2 as it exhibited the highest degree of fibre spreading and the lowest void content. The degree of fibre spreading is defined as the percentage increase of the tow width with respect to the as-received state. In other words, if an as-received fibre tow was spread from 4 mm to 8 mm this was defined as a 100 % degree of fibre spreading.

Table 2. A summary of fibre volume fraction, void content and degree of fibre spreading obtained using three filament winding machines.

Manufacturing method	Fibre volume fraction (%)	Void content (%)	Degree of fibre spreading (%)
Conventional wet-filament winding	63	1.4	-
Clean filament winding Prototype-V	69	1.8	100
Retrofitted clean filament winding (on-site)	67	1.3	50
Clean filament winding Prototype-IV	70	0.8	300

From inspecting Table 2 it can be seen that the CFW and conventional wet-filament winding techniques produced fibre volume fractions of 69 % and 63 % respectively.

The higher CFW fibre volume fractions were attributed to the high winding speeds and optimally spread fibre bundles that could be produced by the new manufacturing technique. Table 2 also shows the comparable void contents produced by the various winding conditions. The lower void contents produced by Prototype-IV were attributed to the multiple fibre spreading characteristics which were present in this injector. Finally, it can also be noticed that vast degrees of fibre spreading were achieved during all of the CFW techniques, it can be seen that the prototype with the largest degree of fibre spreading produced the lowest void content. These results validate the simulations presented in Figure 6.

(b) Image analysis

Typical micrographs obtained from the filament wound tubes manufactured using the conventional resin bath, CFW and those wound on-site using the retrofitted CFW system are presented in Figure 8(a, b and c). The quality of the cylinders produced by the clean filament winding process was shown to be equivalent to those produced by conventional wet-filament winding.

Figure 8: Micrographs showing the quality of filament wound tubes produced by: (A) Conventional wet-filament winding; (B) clean filament winding and (C) retrofitted-clean filament winding on-site.

(c) Hoop tensile strength (split-ring)

Figure 9 shows the normalized tensile strength results for the conventional and clean filament wound cylinders (prototype-V). The data has been normalised to a 69 % fibre volume fraction. The normalised average hoop tensile strengths for the conventional and CFW (prototype-V) techniques were 715 MPa and 717 MPa respectively. This figure shows that the CFW method was capable of producing tubes of comparable hoop tensile strength to those produced using conventional wet-filament winding.

Figure 9. A summary of the normalised hoop tensile strength results for tubes manufactured using conventional wet-filament winding and CFW (prototype-V).

(d) Fibre spreading – Taguchi analysis

Table 3 shows the average spreading values (Levels 1 and 2) determined by the Taguchi analysis described previously. Attention is drawn to the main experimental set-ups i.e. experiments A, B, D and H.

Table 3. Calculation of the average spreading values from the L₁₆ Taguchi analysis.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
Level 1	4.7	5.1	5	4.4	5	5.1	5	4.3	5.2	4.8
Level 2	5.2	4.9	4.9	5.6	5	4.9	5	5.7	4.7	4.5

The average spreading values presented in Table 3 were subjected to an analysis of variance (ANOVA). This involved a comparison of the average spreading values of the Level 1 and Level 2 settings of each parameter from each of the 16 experiments. The P-value results of the ANOVA are presented in Figure 10a. Here a P-value lower than 0.05 was taken as having an influence on fibre spreading with a 95 % confidence level.

Figure 10a shows that the average spreading values of factors D and H produced P-values of 0.02 and 0.01 respectively. As these P-values were lower than the 95 % statistically significant value of 0.05 they were deemed to have a significant influence on fibre spreading. These factors were the fixture configuration and number of fixtures respectively. Figure 10b shows the average spreading results in a response plot. It can clearly be seen that optimum fibre spreading could be achieved from increasing the number of pins and by using static pins. These results were attributed to an increase in frictional fibre forces which produced an increase in fibre tension.

Factor	P-Value	Influence on Fibre Spreading
A	0.2	No Influence
B	0.59	No Influence
C	0.7	No Influence
D	0.02	Influenced
E	0.95	No Influence
F	0.57	No Influence
G	0.83	No Influence
H	0.01	Influenced
I	0.31	No Influence
J	0.4	No Influence

Figure 10a: ANOVA analysis with a confidence level of 95%.

Figure 10b: A response plot showing the influence of Level 1 and Level 2 variations on the four input parameters.

CONCLUSIONS

A modified wet-filament winding technique was developed, evaluated and demonstrated on-site. The key features of this modified filament winding technique were three-fold. Firstly, a fibre spreading station was used to aid transverse impregnation of the fibre tows. Secondly, the conventional resin bath was replaced with a miniature custom-

designed resin impregnation unit. Thirdly, a resin dispensing unit consisted of a pair of precision gear-pumps that were used to deliver the resin and hardener, in the required stoichiometric proportions, to a conventional static mixer. The properties of filament wound tubes manufactured using the conventional and modified techniques demonstrated that the fibre volume fractions and void contents were comparable. The hoop tensile strengths were also similar for the tubes manufactured using the conventional and modified wet-filament winding techniques. Advantages of the modified or clean filament winding technique are as follows: (i) the volume of solvent required to clean the miniature resin impregnation unit is significantly lower when compared to conventional production using a resin bath; (ii) the time required to clean the equipment on-site was approximately 5 minutes, this is a significant reduction when compared to the time taken to clean the five-litre conventional resin bath (60 minutes); and (iii) the volume of waste resin generated is also significantly lower.

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